

Flamingos-2 at Gemini South: Ongoing Upgrades and Upcoming Support of Multi-Object Spectroscopy

Ruben Diaz, Andy Adamson, Janice Lee, Jennifer Lotz (NSF's NOIRLab)

Flamingos-2 (F-2) is a wide-field, near-infrared imager, and long-slit and multi-object spectrograph built by Stephen Eikenberry and his team at the University of Florida [1] that operates on the Gemini South 8m telescope. After a series of refurbishments, F-2 achieved its nominal performance in 2017. Since then it has become the most used near-infrared (NIR) spectrograph at Gemini, with more than 90 refereed publications since 2016, a number growing at the pace of other workhorse NIR instruments in their first years of regular operation.

F-2 provides the widest-field near-infrared imaging capability at Gemini, with a circular field of view (FOV) of 6.1'. The achieved image quality across the whole FOV is on par with the telescope-delivered image quality in the NIR (0.4" FWHM in the *H* band under 20-percentile seeing conditions; Figure 1). The standard *JHKs* set of filters was recently upgraded, adding *Kb* and *Kr*, two high-throughput filters splitting the *K* band to allow demography studies of high-redshift galaxies and young stellar objects.

Figure 1 (previous page). **Top:** F-2 *JHKs* pseudo-color image of NGC 253's central region, showing a 6' x 2.5' part of the circular FOV. The average FWHM is 0.43" across the 6' FOV, meaning that the instrumental PSF permits exploitation of the 20-percentile image quality delivered by the telescope. **Mid-left:** GMMPS (mask design program) showing a mask design on the *Ks* pre-image of NGC 253, including wavelength display. **Bottom Left:** Actual *K*-band flat field taken with the same mask, showing 77 slits of lengths 2–10" and the three alignment star boxes. **Bottom right:** Observing Tool program view on a Digitized Sky Survey red image of NGC 253, marking in red the OIWFS and its patrol field, and in blue the mask FOV. *Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA*

F-2 also provides the longest long-slit spectroscopic capability in the NIR at Gemini. The 4.4' long-slit spectroscopic mode provides average spectral resolution of 2800 over the single bands *J*, *H*, and *K*-long (1.9–2.5 μm) and 1000 with simultaneous coverage on the wider spectral ranges *YJH* and *HK*. As per instrument design, the spectral resolution changes relatively quickly across each spectral range; however, the relatively low internal flexure plus the availability of many OH emission lines in the NIR sky allows accurate wavelength calibration and radial velocity uncertainties of ~5 km s⁻¹ for a single emission line at S/N-25.

In addition to supporting diverse science cases, F-2 is well suited to time-domain astronomy. Gemini's queue operation allows slewing the telescope and acquiring data with F-2 in times as short as three minutes (images) or five minutes (spectra) after a Target of Opportunity has been triggered. For example, F-2 near-infrared images and spectra allowed multiple research teams to form the most complete NIR picture of the gravitational wave event GW170817, covering 25 nights of its aftermath [2]. On the evening twilight of the first day after the researchers pinpointed the location of the optical afterglow, the 8m Gemini South telescope successfully captured some of the first infrared photons ever seen from the merger of two neutron stars.

As part of its Instrument Upgrade Program [3], Gemini started commissioning the Multi-Object Spectroscopy (MOS) mode in 2018. However, a series of mechanical faults due to aging of the On Instrument Wave Front Sensor (OIWFS) mechanism, plus other faults (the most important one related to the closed-cycle refrigeration system), precluded completion of the MOS commissioning in 2019. The final phase of the commissioning was

completed in 2021, and we plan to offer the mode in mid-2022.

The MOS mode currently allows the simultaneous observation of up to 150 targets over an area of 6' x 2', with a maximum of nine masks installed on the instrument per thermal cycle. The OIWFS minimizes spectral losses due to flexure between the focal plane unit and the telescope guiding system, allowing a minimum slit width of 0.54" for zenith distances up to 60 degrees. This allows observing with average spectral resolution of 2000 over the single bands *J*, *H*, and *K*-long (1.9–2.5 μm) and 700 with simultaneous coverage on the wider spectral ranges *YJH* and *HK*. Observing overheads are similar to those in the long-slit mode: maximization of the number of slits on point-source targets or the observation of extended targets require an overhead larger than 100% of the on-source time due to the need for offsetting to obtain sky frames.

F-2 masks (Figure 2) can be designed with targets selected from pre-images or catalog pseudo-images and can be cut with the lasers at either the Gemini North or the Gemini South site. The current public Gemini IRAF package includes recipes and examples for MOS and long-slit data reduction, and imaging data can be processed within the Gemini DRAGONS Python-based platform.

Gemini continues to upgrade its operations, instrumentation, and user support to provide its community with essential scientific capabilities for the 2020s and to preserve and enhance diverse science, ensuring benefits to the broadest possible set of users, as outlined in its Scientific Strategic Plan [4]. The next F-2 upgrades, ongoing in the CP instrument laboratory, will improve its overall spectroscopy performance (including the MOS

mode). The *YJH/HK* broadband spectroscopic filters will be replaced by new versions, increasing the spectroscopic throughput in the *R-1000* modes by ~9% (*HK*) and ~12% (*YJH*) and making the response function significantly flatter. Another ongoing upgrade will increase by two the number of filter slots, allowing us to offer the *J*-low and *Y* filters permanently, as requested by several user teams. In addition, the instrument's thermal insulation will be improved to allow more thermal stability, especially in the MOS dewar. Finally, we have initiated a study to probe the performance of the F-2 spectroscopic modes when used with the multi-conjugate adaptive optics system GeMS and plan to issue a feasibility report in 2023.

References:

- [1] Eikenberry, S., et al. 2008, *Proc. SPIE*, 7014, 70140V
- [2] Chornock, R., et al. 2017, *ApJL*, , 848, L19
- [3] Diaz, R., et al. 2018, *Proc. SPIE*, 10702, 107023R
- [4] Blakeslee, J. P., et al. 2019, arXiv:1909.09196

The contributors to F-2 MOS commissioning are Andy Adamson, Gonzalo Diaz, Ruben Diaz, Stephen Eikenberry, German Gimeno, Percy Gomez, Scot Kleinman, Janice Lee, Jennifer Lotz, Bryan Miller, Marcelo Mora, Gabriel Perez, Pablo Prado, Steven Raines, Rolando Rogers, Roberto Rojas, Rene Rutten, Ricardo Salinas, Mischa Schirmer, Karleyne Silva, Chris Simpson, Andrew Stephens, and James Turner.

Figure 2. M93 mask with 78 slits, 1" × 3" length each, and 3 alignment star boxes. **Top:** GMMPS mask design and *K_s* pre-image. Note that the intensity level display is non-linear and shows the low-level artifacts in the processed image, due to the pre-image dithering pattern and the presence of many bright stars in the observed field. **Center:** OT configuration. **Bottom:** The mask (anodized Al) with the slits cut with the Gemini South laser cutter. *Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA*

Mask Field of View	6' × 2'	Targets from F-2 pre-image or catalog
Number of 4.5" length slits	72	Nodding along the slits (100% on source)
Number of 1.8" length slits	153	Offsetting to sky position (50% on source)
Spectral coverage	0.97–2.48 μm	<i>YJH, HK, J, H, K</i> -long band modes
Spectral Resolution	700 / 2000	Single / Broadband, 0.54" slit
Spatial image quality	0.4"	<i>H</i> band, IQ 20-percentile observing conditions

Table 1. MOS capability